

Land Use and Performance of Large-Scale Agricultural Investment in South West Ethiopia Regional State

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Abstract

Recently Ethiopia's open-door policy has encouraged investment aimed at improving agriculture, deriving economic development, and promoting technology transfer to local communities (MoA Policy, 2024). The South West Ethiopia favorable conditions, particularly agro-ecological and regional stability, attracted more investors. However, there is noticeable limited empirical studies on land use and performance of Large-scale Agricultural Investment in the region. This study seeks to address this gap in the literature by examining the investment patterns, employment contribution, and investment challenges in agriculture in South Western Ethiopia (SWETH). Capital investment trends, export earnings, employment prospects, and land use by regions are investigated using descriptive and inferential statistics. This study found that a significant variation in the investment pattern, with Bench Sheko and Konta being highly skewed and large-scale investments (LSAIs), while Sheka and West Omo depict relatively even trends. LSAIs dominate export-oriented tea and coffee markets, possessing huge regional market share. The finding of this study also show production system in the region is under the threat of climate risks due the reliance on rain-fed farming and the lack of well-established irrigation infrastructures. In additions, infrastructural constraints, poor access to finance, natural factors (floods and droughts) and lack of skill and managerial are key challenges facing Agricultural investors in the region. To address these challenges, this study recommends the extension of irrigation infrastructure and increased employment opportunities, enhanced access to markets, investments diversification, and development research and technology adoption. Finally, the study advocates for the adoption of gender-sensitive policies, improved financial access, and strengthen stakeholder's collaboration to foster inclusive and sustainable agricultural investment.

Keywords: Agricultural Investment, Land use, Performance, Investment ill this Challenges, South West Ethiopia

1. Introduction

Agriculture is the backbone of the African economy; which is the primary source of livelihood for most of Africa's population. It plays a role of great importance in economic activity across all African countries as it relates closely to continental priorities such as poverty eradication, hunger alleviation, enhancement of intra-African trade, industrialization, economic diversification, sustainable natural resource management, and job creation (NEPAD, 2017). Agricultural Investment now days serve as a mechanism for responding to events such the global food, financial, and energy crises of 2007/08. In this regard, after 1992, Ethiopian adopted an open-door policy regarding the leasing of land to domestic and foreign investors, covering over 2.2 million hectares (Amanuel, 2019). The policy is intended to modernize agriculture, create jobs, and ensure

food security. Recent reform on investment policy, in 2024, will further emphasize how private agriculture promote economic and social development.

Empirical research shows that, though such investments are promise for huge economic growth, its socioeconomic and environmental influence become debate among scholars. The majority of the literature documented Smallholders farmer displacement, uneven distributions of benefits that can be obtained, loss of biodiversity and land degradation as negative impact of large-scale agricultural investment, even though some governance and instructional framework as major factors hindering its effectiveness(Gasisa et al., 2024; Guyalo et al., 2022; Mulaw et al., 2023; Zaehringer et al., 2021). The large-scale agricultural investment (LSAIs) generate more employment and provides opportunities for technology transfer in agriculture. Gasisa et al. (2024) point out that LSAIs in Ethiopia increased about 30% in employment opportunities. Nevertheless, this benefit arises with equity issues due to the usual inequitably distributed advantages among communities. For instance, agrarian investment brought restrictions on access to land and natural resources and caused damages to household welfare through a number of malpractices (Gasisa et al., 2024; Mulaw et al., 2023).

However, the food security research by Guyalo et al. (2022) and Bekele et al. (2021) shows negative effect of Large Scale Agricultural Investment (LSAIs) on the local communities, which indicated by people displacement and LSAIs unfair utilization of fertile land. In addition, Ali et al. (2019) stated that the effect of LSAIs on job creating and improving neighboring small holder livelihood is not significant, but did not identified its role impacting youth unemployment. The issue specially needs paid more attention which is the critical issue in Ethiopia. Other studies focused on the introduction and access of technologies by LSAIs and adoption by smallholders, although as the Knowledge and skill transfer to the local community have also received slight attention in previous research, for instance Duguma et al.(2024), Mulaw et al.(2023) and Wolde & Tolossa (2019). Although there are constraining factors, the role of policy and governance in promoting private sector involvement in agricultural development is vital in Ethiopia(Goshu & Dong, 2018; Haileslasie, 2018). In addition, effectiveness of existing policies in regulating LSAIs and protecting local rights, the transparency of land acquisition processes and the accountability of investors and government agencies remain underexplored.

Despite the growing emphasis on Large Scale Agricultural Investment, existing studies have not sufficiently addressed how regional heterogeneity affects the operation of agricultural land use and performance of Agricultural investment. This gaps in knowledge potentially limit understanding of the effectiveness in land-use planning and policy formulation. The South West Ethiopia regional state, which is pivotal point for Agricultural Investments, possess relatively high land potential and favorable agro-ecological condition. According to the 2024 report of this region, there are about 480 large-scale agricultural investors in this region, currently utilizing about 221,734 hectares of land across the six zones and thirty-four districts that make up the region. While this indicates significant activity, limited has been conducted on large-scale agricultural investments (LAIs) in Southwest Ethiopia, particularly in relation to land use patterns and socio-environmental consequences, realistic economic contributions and feasible interventions.

The existing literatures primarily focused on the socioeconomic impact of investments, with little attention given to critical issues such as deforestation, and soil degradation, factor that heavy

constrain investors decisions. Moreover, there is need for comprehensive assessment of productivity of the LSAIs to evaluate the long-term viability and developmental impact. This study aims to fill these gaps and provide holistic understating of LSAIs in Southwest Ethiopia thereby supporting the development of policies that foster both economic growth and environmental sustainability.

Specifically, the research investigates major land use choices, employment impact, and the challenges facing Agricultural Investment in the region. Employing both qualitative and quantitative research method, this study contributes to the body of literature on land use transformations and agricultural modernization by carrying out a comprehensive analysis of agricultural land investments in Southwest Ethiopia.

2. Methodology

2.1. Description of the Study Area

The South West Ethiopia Regional State officially designated in 2021 as one of Ethiopia's eleven regional states, is outstandingly noted for ecological and agricultural diversity. The region is characterized by a range of agro-ecological zones representing transitional rainforests at an elevation of 450-650 meters typically semi-deciduous forests to evergreen montane forests which are found higher up. This combination of richness in ecological forms makes the region ideal for a wide range of agricultural productivities and growing conditions, including the production of export cash crops such as coffee and tea.

In 2010, an area within the Kaffa zone was recognized as a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve as part of the Man and the Biosphere Programme. Officially named the "Kafa Biosphere Reserve" it is one of the first two biosphere reserves in Ethiopia and aims to protect the natural environment and foster sustainable development in the region. This combination of ecological richness and cultural history makes the South West Ethiopia Regional State a strategic, culturally rich and highly sensitive arena for large-scale agricultural investment studies. To this extent, understanding the performance investment practices important to the development of appropriate policies and frameworks.

2.2 Research Method and Design

This study employed sequential mixed-methods explanatory research design, which combines both quantitative and qualitative methods to provide an in-depth analysis of land use and performance of agricultural investment in south west Ethiopia regional state. These approaches involve initial collection and analysis of quantitative data with regard to land use and performance of agricultural investment, followed by the qualitative data collection and analyze aimed complementing and enriching the quantitative analysis.

2.3. Sampling Design

The choice of South Western Ethiopia is purposive, which is due to attractiveness of the region to investor, ecological suitability and its stability relative to another region in Ethiopia. The Study targeted key stakeholders involved or affected by agricultural investments in Southwest Ethiopia, primarily investors and government authority. Regarding investors population, all individuals are manageable in size and thus allowed for the census sampling, ensuring full inclusion investors registered in the region. So, all 315 investors were selected for quantitative research purpose. These

includes all formally registered land lease investors. In addition, a total of 15 key informant interviewee were selected purposively. These were drawn from zones, regional office, Local community and Federal government office.

2.4 Data Collections Tools and Analysis

The study employed a mixed-methods approach, utilizing Kobo Tool for data collection. Primary data were collected from investors using structured survey tools. These surveys were intended to capture quantitative information regarding land use patterns, and challenges confronted by agricultural investors. Complementing the structured surveys, basic qualitative data were collected through key informant interviews with senior officials, experts, and community members, to better understand the practices as well as advantages and challenges of agricultural investments at regional, zonal, and district levels.

Qualitative data from KIIs and FGDs were analyzed using content analysis based on patterns and themes about governance, policy gaps, and investment challenges. Descriptive statistics was used to analyze quantitative data from structured surveys included mean, median, standard deviation, and frequency distributions, with the support of statistical software such as JAMOVI and SPSS. This provided a good overview of the data, but very importantly allowed researchers to identify trends and variations in responses among stakeholder groups. One-Way ANOVA using JAMOVI and SPSS was also conducted for mean comparisons between Zones to ascertain statistically significant differences regarding agricultural investments. This approach, integrated into the best of both worlds, provided insight into agricultural investments in a robust manner.

2.5 Ethical Consideration

To make the participants understand the aim of study, the potential procedures involved, the potential risks and the anticipated benefits were clearly communicate , as recommended by (Israel & Hay, 2007). Participants were informed that at any point of participating in the research study they have right to quit taking part in the research study without negative consequences. The researcher emphasized that the study participants could choose not to answer any question they were uncomfortable with and that there would be no penalties for choosing to withdraw from the study at any time (Israel & Hay, 2007). The researcher has obtained ethical approval from ethics committee of the University.

3. Results

3.1. Patterns and Distributions of Agricultural Investments

Table 1 provides the trends in agricultural capital investment across various zones in South Western Ethiopia. Different zones practice different levels of investment with varying patterns.

Table 1. Patterns of Agricultural Capital Investment in South Western Ethiopia (in Million)

Zone	Mean	Median	Sum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Bench Sheko	48.6	14.3	2,430	6.761	46.951
Dawro	28	14.5	672	3.882	16.847
Kaffa	18.9	10.8	2,850	3.491	15.753

Zone	Mean	Median	Sum	Skewness	Kurtosis
Konta	67.6	25	1,280	4.266	18.43
Sheka	17	10.4	392	0.978	0.13
West Omo	30.5	25	1,310	1.382	2.152

Sources: **Author Computation using Jamovi**

The capital investment patterns of Southwestern Ethiopia agriculture exhibit considerable variation across zones, with variations in the proportion invested. The average capital investment in Bench Sheko (48.6 million) is significantly larger than the median (14.3 million) and reflective of a heavily skewed right distribution. The extreme skewness (6.761) and kurtosis (46.951) also validate the same. Konta reflects such a wide difference between the mean (67.6 million) and median (25 million) and exhibits a skewness of 4.266, implying that huge-sized investments predominate the flow of capital but to a lesser extent than is seen in Bench Sheko. The kurtosis value of 18.430 suggests a heavy investment weighting in a few large values.

Sheka and West Omo zones, however, have more even investment patterns. In Sheka, the mean (17 million) and median (10.7 million) are similar, with a skewness of only 0.978, which suggests that investments are evenly spread throughout the zone. Similarly, the skewness for West Omo is 1.382, indicating moderate right-skewed data where some very large investments have a bit more influence on the mean (30.5 million) than on the median (25 million), but even then, far less extreme than for Bench Sheko and Konta. In Dawro and Kaffa, the median and mean are closer, but still show some right-skewness, with mean values (28 million and 18.9 million, respectively) larger than the median values. The skewness values of 3.882 for Dawro and 3.491 for Kaffa indicate that while high investments are being made, the distribution is not as concentrated as it is for Bench Sheko or Konta.

Table 2. Distribution of Agricultural Investment (Pairwise Comparison)

ANOVA (Non-parametric)	χ^2	df	p
	22.9	5	<.001
Capital Investment		W	p
Bench Sheko	Dawro	-0.858	0.991
Bench Sheko	Kaffa	-2.801	0.354
Bench Sheko	Konta	2.547	0.465
Bench Sheko	Sheka	-1.856	0.779
Bench Sheko	West Omo	2.404	0.532
Dawro	Kaffa	-1.426	0.915
Dawro	Konta	2.612	0.436
Dawro	Sheka	-1.053	0.976
Dawro	West Omo	2.544	0.467
Kaffa	Konta	4.24	0.032
Kaffa	Sheka	0.358	1.000
Kaffa	West Omo	5.465	0.002

Konta	Sheka	-3.11	0.238
Konta	West Omo	-0.616	0.998
Sheka	West Omo	3.579	0.115

Source: Author own computation-using Jamovi. **Note:** Capital investment pairwise comparisons, based on Kruskal-Wallis One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

Table 2 provided evidence on whether variation in investment importantly make difference among zones. The Kruskal-Wallis One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) has been used to identify whether variation in agricultural investment is significantly different between the zones in Southwestern Ethiopia. The overall Chi-squared (χ^2) value of 22.9 on 5 degrees of freedom with a p-value of less than 0.001 indicates that there is significant variation in capital investment between at least some of the zones.

The pairwise test between West Omo and Kaffa gives a W statistic of 5.465 and a p-value of 0.002, which is significant. This indicates a large difference in capital investment between Kaffa and West Omo. This suggests that the capital investments in these two areas differ significantly. In addition, The W statistic for Kaffa and Konta is 4.24 and p = 0.032, which is also statistically significant.

3.2. Economic impact of Large-scale agricultural investment

Table 3 shows that LSAIs are dominating export markets for these commodities and play a very crucial role in their production and trade. For instance, in Sheka 90% of coffee and 100% of tea exports come from LSAIs, 60% in Kafa of coffee and 100% from tea. Likewise, 100% of coffee exports come from LSAIs in Dawro, and Konta 50% of coffee exports and 100% from tea. This adds up to how significant LSAIs have contributed to enhancing the export drive of SWETH.

Table 3. Commodity Exported from South Western Ethiopia

Zone	Total Export			Share of LSAIs	
	Coffee	Tea	Other	Coffee	Tea
Bench sheko	27,657.86	-	5,948.93		
Sheka	14,296.38	1,708.75	7,994.45	80%	100%
Kafa	11,888.62	4,811.11	9,827.54	90%	100%
West Omo	942.41	-	1,213.96	60%	100%
Dawro	0.00	-	20,919.00	100%	-
Konta	9.76	-	8,008.01	50%	100%
Total	54,795.02	6,519.86	53,911.89	40%	100%

Sources: Region Trade and Investment office

In addition, from the result in table 3, the total export values further underline the economic importance of these crops. Leading in coffee exports, Sheka with 14,296.38 units; Kafa with 11,888.62 units and finally, Bench Sheko with 27,657.86 units. Tea also, Sheka with exports of 1,708.75 units and Kafa with 4,811.11 units of tea. It indicates in the export share that larger investments drive through productivity, quality improvement, and market accessibility, which in turn enhances the competitiveness of agricultural products from SWETH in the world market.

Table 4 reveals contribution of Agricultural investments in creating employment opportunities across SWETH. Accordingly, Kaffa has the highest male employment (2,281) and male contract employment (9,847), and Konta has the lowest male employment (82.0) and male contract employment (481). The female employment is significantly lower in all zones, with the highest female employment (452) and female contract employment (7,652) in Kaffa and the lowest (22.0 and 236, respectively) for Konta. Regions like Sheko Bench and Sheka reveal moderate to high levels of male employment but minimal female employment, which reflect the historical gender imbalances in employment. Dawuro and West Omo have lower overall employment levels, reflecting job generation constraints within these regions. These disparities reinforce the need for gender-sensitive policy and targeted investment that will support men and women equally from jobs in agriculture.

Table 4. Agricultural Investment Employment in South Western Ethiopia By Zones

Zone_1	Male_E	Female_E	Male_EContr	Female_Econtr
Bench Sheko	2179	368	8588	1609
Dawro	229	64.0	878	571
Kaffa	2281	452	9847	7652
Konta	82.0	22.0	481	236
Sheka	1444	207	6049	4110
West Omo	399	67.0	2326	1046

Source: Author Computation using Jamovi

3.3 Agricultural Investment Land use in South West Ethiopia

Table 5 provides the distribution of agricultural land use across different zones in SWETH. The result revealed considerable differences in total area, cultivated land, rainfed cultivation, irrigated cultivation, and uncultivated land. The analysis presents a comparison of land use in six zones (Bench Sheko, Dawro, Kaffa, Konta, Sheka, and West Omo) focusing on cultivated and uncultivated land and the two modes of cultivation, rain-fed and irrigated. Kaffa has a total land area of 30,422 units and is therefore the biggest zone, followed by Bench Sheko (29,116 units) and West Omo (18,698units); Konta has the smallest land area (4,377 units). Regarding cultivated land, the zone that has, once again, the maximum area is Kaffa with 21,954 units, followed, however, by Bench Sheko (18,428) and Sheka (11,351), whereas Konta has the minimum area under cultivation.

Table 5. Distribution of Agricultural Land use (Hectare) disruption by Zones

Zone_1	land	cultivated	uncultivated	raincult	irrigcult
Bench Sheko	29116	18428	10688	18086	342
Dawro	5017	2308	2709	2067	241
Kaffa	30422	21954	8468	21883	71.2

Zone_1	land	cultivated	uncultivated	raincult	irrigcult
Konta	4377	1288	3089	1128	160
Sheka	11908	11351	557	11351	0.00
West Omo	18698	9247	9452	9048	199

Sources: Author Computation using Jamovi

In addition, the result shows that uncultivated land is maximum in West Omo (9,452), Bench Sheko (10,688), and Kaffa (8,468), whereas the minimum uncultivated land is in Sheka (557). Rain-fed cultivation is a major practice in all zones; the biggest area occupied by rain-fed cultivation is Kaffa (21,883), Bench Sheko (18,086), and Sheka (11,351). It has an extremely small area for irrigated cultivation with maximum area found in Bench Sheko (342), followed by West Omo (199), and Dawro (241). Of importance is that Sheka is totally dependent on rain-fed methods, with no irrigated cultivation (0.00 units). As indicated from the data, there is a predominance of rain-fed agriculture across the zones with irrigation practice almost absent, and this presents a possibility for agricultural enhancement or extension in many respects, especially in areas that remain uncultivated, which include West Omo and Bench Sheko.

Table 6 provides the descriptive statistics on agricultural land use and crop practices among different zones in South Western Ethiopia (SWETH). Having the highest number of observations (N=172) and highest total land area (Sum=54,119 hectares), land chosen for Coffee production dominantly. However, the large difference between its mean (315) and median (131), and its high standard deviation (SD=899.7), indicates a skewed distribution, with some large coffee farms taking up more than their proportionate share of land. Mixed crop systems, with the second-largest number of observations (N=103) and largest mean land use (374 hectares), indicate utilization of land for more extensive mixed farm.

Table 6. Agricultural Land Use Choice (Per hectare)

Crop system	N	Mean	Median	Sum	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Cereal	11	239	200.00	2624	216.9	50.0000	829
Coffee	172	315	131.00	54119	899.7	8.5000	9948
Fruit	9	138	100.00	1243	91.9	39.7100	305
Livestock	11	118	7.67	1300	354.7	0.0135	1187
Mixed	103	374	200.00	38544	475.5	6.4000	2750
Pulse	9	190	200.00	1709	65.4	50.0000	300

Sources: Author Computation using SPSS

On the other hand, Cereal and Pulse systems exhibit more evenly divided land use with similar mean and median values, though cereals are more diverse in land use. Livestock systems have the lowest median land use (7.67 hectares) and a very low minimum (0.0135 hectares), which reflects

the predominance of small-scale farms, though there are a few large-scale outliers. Fruit farming has the lowest range and lowest cumulative land use with a Sum=1,243 hectares, appears to be less common and operated on smaller sizes. Overall, the numbers indicate the dominance of the Coffee and Mixed systems of agricultural land use, while Livestock and Fruit systems are more focused.

3.4 Challenges of Agricultural Investment in South West Ethiopia

The findings in this study indicate the challenges faced by agricultural investments in South Western Ethiopia (SWETH) including facility related issues, policy and institutions, managerial, skill and natural challenges. Table 7 indicates company lack of facilities which poses significant limitation on agricultural investments, with the majority of reported instances being the lack of the accommodation facility for staff (27.4% of answers, 76.0% of instances) and administrative offices (26.2% of answers, 72.6% of instances). In addition, the lack of input warehouses (20.0% of answers, 55.4% of instances) and crop warehouses (20.1% of answers, 55.7% of instances) further adds to operational inefficiencies. Only 5.2% of the replies (14.5% of cases) had no issues with company buildings. Implications for agricultural development are that investment needs to be undertaken in facilities needed in order to raise efficiency in operations, reduce post-harvest losses, and improve working conditions for employees. The possible reasons for such constraints would be low rural infrastructure investment, high construction costs, and logistical challenges in remote areas.

Table 7. Facility Constraints

	Responses		Percent of Cases
	Frequency	Percent	
Administration office	215	26.2%	72.6%
Employee house	225	27.4%	76.0%
Input Warehouse	164	20.0%	55.4%
Crop Warehouse	165	20.1%	55.7%
None	43	5.2%	14.5%
Other	9	1.1%	3.0%
Total	821	100.0%	277.4%

Sources: Author Computation using SPSS

Table 8 shows policy and institutional issues which posed significant barriers to agricultural investments. The most critical issue is restricted access to the fundamental infrastructure (21.7% of responses, 80.1% of cases), such as roads, telecommunication, electricity, and irrigation networks. These major constraints include limited access to better inputs and new technology (8.9% of responses, 32.9% of cases), research support shortcomings (8.0% of responses, 29.6% of cases), and credit facilities aimed at irrigated agriculture exclusively (8.1% of responses, 29.9% of cases). Besides, issues such as fragmented government structures (2.9% of the responses, 10.6% of the cases) and governance (2.5% of the responses, 9.3% of the cases) also limit investment growth. Possible explanations for these include lack of coordination among the stakeholders, underfinancing, and insufficient focus on rainfed farming systems that prevail in the region.

Table 9 provides managerial and skill constraining agricultural investments. The most prevalent issue is capacity problems (29.9% of the answers, 60.6% of the cases), including limited exposure to the sector, financial constraints, and insufficient qualified human resources. The other important limitations are the lack of environmental impact assessment (EIA) reports and poor implementation (27.8% of responses, 56.4% of cases) and poor camp facility organization (21.0% of responses, 42.5% of cases).

Table 8. Policy and Institutional challenges

Constraints	Responses		Percent of Cases
	Frequency	Percent	
Fragmented government structure	32	2.9%	10.6%
Absence of policy and strategic guidelines	12	1.1%	4.0%
Weak access to improved input and technology supply	99	8.9%	32.9%
Poor linkage among stakeholders	37	3.3%	12.3%
Inability to Identify potentially ready for investors	31	2.8%	10.3%
Weak participation of local community	29	2.6%	9.6%
Poor access to basic Infrastructures	241	21.7%	80.1%
Lack of good governance and rent seeking behavior	28	2.5%	9.3%
Lack of insurance service	40	3.6%	13.3%
Weak support	70	6.3%	23.3%
Poor Research support for large scale agri. Investment	89	8.0%	29.6%
Lack of digitalized service support	69	6.2%	22.9%
Complicated bureaucracy for loan access	44	4.0%	14.6%
Credit access facility focus only on irrigated agriculture	90	8.1%	29.9%
Lack of swift response for further investment expansion	46	4.1%	15.3%
Lack of commercial oriented extension support & service	25	2.3%	8.3%
Security Problem	81	7.3%	26.9%
Lack of Good governance and long bureaucracy	22	2.0%	7.3%
Several checkpoints within and across regions	15	1.4%	5.0%
Other	10	0.9%	3.3%
Total	1110	100.0%	368.8%
Sources: Author Computation using SPSS			

Moreover, lack of market access (3.2% of responses, 6.6% of cases) and land conflicts on arable land (4.0% of responses, 8.1% of cases) also constitute serious impediments. Impacts on agricultural development include the investor capacity that can be improved by training, finance, and human resources. Improving the enforcement of EIA reports and management of camp facilities can optimize operating efficiency and sustainability. Possible reasons for such constraints include lack of access to training and fiscal resources, inadequate application of environmental policy, and poor infrastructure and market linkages.

Table 9. Managerial and Skill Constraints

Constrains	Responses		Percent of Cases
	Frequency	Percent	
Capacity issues	157	29.9%	60.6%
Farmland Conflict with neighbor farmers/ investors	21	4.0%	8.1%
Corrupted mindset and to benefit basic privileges	3	0.6%	1.2%
Unable to discharging social corporate responsibility	9	1.7%	3.5%
Miss use of use of privileges for unplanned activities	20	3.8%	7.7%
Lack of market Access	17	3.2%	6.6%
Transfer of land use right to third party	3	0.6%	1.2%
Lack of EIA report and poor implementation	146	27.8%	56.4%
Poor organization of camp facility	110	21.0%	42.5%
Absence of business plan	28	5.3%	10.8%
Other	11	2.1%	4.2%
Total	525	100.0%	202.7%
Sources: Author Computation using SPSS			

Table 10 shows the natural factors increased the challenges containing by agricultural investment. The greatest constraint is the high incidence and prevalence of disease (77.8% of responses, 88.9% of illustrations), which impact crop and animal health. Some of the other problems are drought occurrence (11.8% of responses, 13.5% of cases) and flood occurrence (10.4% of responses, 11.9% of cases). The implications for agricultural development are making investments in disease control interventions, climate-resilient agriculture practice, and irrigation facilities to minimize these risks. Some of the probable causes for these problems are the susceptibility of the region to climate variability and lack of good access to veterinary and plant health services.

Table 10. Natural challenges faced Agricultural Investment

Calamities	Responses		Percent of Cases
	Frequency	Percent	
Frequent incidence and prevalence of disease	112	77.8%	88.9%
Drought occurrence	17	11.8%	13.5%
Incidence of flood	15	10.4%	11.9%
Total	144	100.0%	114.3%

4. Discussion

This study identified considerable variations in investments in agricultural capital across zones of SWETH, with Bench Sheko and Konta having highly skewed investment distributions held in the hands of large investments, while Sheka and West Omo account more evenly spread investments in capital. This finding is in line with Abobatta et al. (2024) and Kuzmichl (2022), where they

discuss the need for balanced land qualification policies and the risk of concentration of large-scale investments. In addition, the unequal distribution of investment among Bench Sheko and Konta agricultural investments could lead to the marginalization of households and unequal economic benefit which confirm with a finding of Abdallah et al. (2024). The results are again consistent with Ju et al. (2024) and Ni (2023), who note that, while scale effects and adoption of technology can increase productivity, they also point to inequality in sharing the benefits.

In SWETH, agricultural investments strongly contribute to the export promotion of high-value commodities like coffee and tea. This is in line with Sullivan (2022), stating that contract farming and high-value crops can enhance productivity but also drive inequity. The agricultural export markets in Sheka and Kaffa are dominated by large Scale agricultural investments, which reflects uneven economic importance leading to possible inclusivity and sustainability concerns, as noted by Muder et al. (2024) and Oberlack et al. (2021). The agricultural investments in SWETH create job opportunities; however, there seems to be some disparity among genders. Employment opportunities favors males than t of females. This backs the calls for gender-sensitive policies in agricultural investment by Workneh and Kumar (2023). Gasisa et al. (2024) also indicated that large Scale agricultural investments posed socio-economic challenges, which included job uncertainty and differential payment.

This study indicates that rain-fed agriculture is the main form of farming practiced in SWETH. Any irrigation of any kind was scarcely practiced. This observation resonated Ge et al. (2022), who underscore the influence of the natural environment and production factors on patterns of land use. The main use of rain-fed, especially in Sheka, makes such agricultural systems prone to climate variability as reported by Liao et al. (2021) and Zaehring et al. (2021). It is also seen that coffee and mixed-crop systems are dominantly practiced, paralleled to what Zhang et al. (2023) denote as an urgent need to develop land-management practices that optimize sustainability in agricultural outputs.

The study outlines various constraints to agriculture investments in SWETH. The first constraint relates to facilities which includes lack of warehouses and staff quarters that prevent operational efficiencies, hence coinciding with the views expressed by Harnaha (2024), an advocate of a favorable investment climate with government assistance. Secondly, institutional and policy constraints including limited access to technology, research, and credit facilities, constrain investment evolution as argued by Aragie (2024), who stressed the need for specific investment measures and advanced production technologies. Thirdly, managerial and competence constraints, for example, capacity shortfalls and poor environmental impact assessments (EIAs,) execution are major issues according to Butkova (2022), who views modernization and financial management improvement in agriculture as necessity. Last but not least, natural hazards, such as widespread disease and climatic accidents in terms of many floods and droughts, threaten agricultural productivity, as stated by Liao et al. (2021), imploring the need for climate-resilient practices and thorough mitigation.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

The findings of this study highlight the critical role played by Large scale agricultural investment in South Western Ethiopia. It provides insights on the patterns, impacts, and challenges against agricultural investments, which coincide with- and broadened the empirical literature. South

Western Ethiopia agricultural investment is marked with extensive regional differentials, both in the patterning of the capital, influence on employment as well as utilization of land. Benefits of the Agricultural investment in promoting export and generating employment but with diverse socio-economic and environmental challenges, which call for a balanced approach of economic growth with sustainability, inclusivity, and resilience to address.

On the basis of these findings, thus, promoting private sector participation in agricultural sector is necessary for optimizing agricultural investment toward long-term economic growth and sustainability of the regional state. The government and other stakeholders need to act on fostering irrigation systems to attend to limited derogations, increase financing and policy-wide frameworks, invest in infrastructure, and advocate gender-based policies to improve Labor participation. These recommendations will lead to a policy and practice framework for evidence-based sustainable agricultural development in Ethiopia and beyond.

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